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CHANGES IN THE MORPHOLOGICAL AND MORPHOMETRIC PARAMETERS OF THE GASTRIC WALL IN POLYPRAGMASS WITH ANTI-INFLAMMATORY DRUGS

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ABSTRACT

In the modern world, the creation and introduction of a large number of medicines is growing rapidly, which, on the one hand, can cure or improve the patient's condition, and on the other hand, seriously harm health. The desire to increase the effectiveness of treatment, to help the patient get rid of all the diseases he has developed inevitably leads to the use of a large number of drugs (DM) - polypharmacy. Polypharmacy is a serious health problem, as it is clinically manifested by a decrease in the effectiveness of pharmacotherapy and the development of serious side effects, as well as a significant increase in health care costs.

Keywords: Stomach, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), morphology, and experiment.

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ИЗМЕНЕНИЕ МОРФОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ И МОРФОМЕТРИЧЕСКИХ ПАРАМЕТРОВ СТЕНКИ ЖЕЛУДКА В ПОЛИПРАГМАЗИИ ПРОТИВОВОСПАЛИТЕЛЬНЫМИ ПРЕПАРАТАМИ**АННОТАЦИЯ**

В современном мире быстрыми темпами растет создание и внедрение большого количества лекарственных средств, которые, с одной стороны, могут вылечить или улучшить состояние пациента, а с другой стороны, серьезно навредить здоровью. Стремление повысить

эффективность лечения, помочь больному избавиться от всех развившихся у него заболеваний неизбежно приводит к использованию большого количества лекарственных препаратов (ЛС) - полипрагмазии. Полипрагмазия является серьезной проблемой здравоохранения, так как клинически проявляется снижением эффективности фармакотерапии и развитием серьезных побочных эффектов, а также значительным увеличением затрат на здравоохранение.

Ключевые слова: Желудок, нестероидные противовоспалительные препараты (НПВП), морфология и эксперимент.

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POLIPRAGMAZIYAGA QARSHI PREPARATLAR BILAN O'RNATILADIGAN POLIPRAGMAZIYADAGI OSHQOZON MORFOLOGIK VA MORFOMETRIK PARAMETRLARNING O'ZGARISHI

ANNOTATSIYA

Zamonaviy dunyoda, bir tomondan, bemorning ahvolini davolaydigan yoki yaxshilashi mumkin bo'lgan, boshqa tomondan esa sog'likka jiddiy zarar yetkazadigan juda ko'p miqdordagi dori vositalarini yaratish va amaliy sog'liqni saqlashga joriy etish jadal sur'atlar bilan o'sib bormoqda. Davolanish samaradorligini oshirish, bemorga unda rivojlangan barcha kasalliklardan xalos bo'lishga yordam berish istagi muqarrar ravishda ko'p miqdordagi dori vositalarini (DV) – polipragmaziya olib keladi. Polipragmaziya jiddiy sog'liqni saqlash muammosidir, chunki u klinik jihatdan farmakoterapiya samaradorligining pasayishi va jiddiy nojo'ya ta'sirlarning rivojlanishi, shuningdek, sog'liqni saqlash xarajatlarining sezilarli darajada oshishi bilan namoyon bo'ladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Oshqozon, steroid bo'lmagan yallig'lanishga qarshi dorilar (NPVP), morfologiya va tajriba.

INTRODUCTION

The study of various aspects of pathogenesis and morphogenesis of gastrointestinal tract disease constitutes a significant part that gradually grows into a separate, essential field of medical science. To date, various changes in the stomach mucous membrane are described, arising from the effects of various types of damaging factors: chemical, physical, infectious; At the same time, morphological changes of the structure of the mucous membrane of the stomach of the GT, with the effects of various types of damaging agents, have their peculiarities [Minushkin O.N. et al., 2013; Karateev A.E., 2011]. Morphological changes of SGD and pathogenesis of chronic gastritis of the disease have their peculiarities for different forms of gastritis [Minushkin O.N. et al., 2013]. It is generally accepted that *Helicobacter pylori*, associated gastritis, is the most common, but the so-called NSAID gastropathy (one of the varieties of chemical gastritis, type C), damage to the gastric mucosa caused by the intake of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), is no less relevant. Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are among the most commonly prescribed drugs by physicians to treat various conditions in patients of all age groups [Hawkey C.I. et al., 2011]. Various clinical symptoms of inflammatory diseases combined with limited possibilities of etiotropic therapy, a large number of symptomatic agents became the causes of polypragmasia. Unreasonable treatment often slows down the natural healing process. Recently, the gastrointestinal tract is considered an essential component of the general defense of the body. [Nasyrova S.Z. et al., 2021].

Despite the study, questions related to the features of changes in the proliferation of the epithelium of the gastric mucosa with prolonged use of NSAIDs remain poorly studied and controversial.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

To study the morphometric parameters of the stomach of healthy white rats in postnatal ontogenesis from 3 months of age to 6 months and the simultaneous use of several antiinflammatory drugs.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The work was carried out on white outbred male rats aged from 3 to 6 months in the usual conditions of the vivarium. The timing of the study was chosen by us based on data on the structural and functional characteristics of the stomach and age periodization of laboratory animals. The morphological changes of the gastric mucosa were studied experimentally in 40 white outbred male rats weighing 160-220g. Autopsy materials were used as material for the study. For general morphology, pieces were excised from each stomach and solidified in 10% neutral formalin. After washing for 2–4h in running water, it was dehydrated in concentrated alcohol and chloroform, then embedded in paraffin and prepared blocks. On paraffin blocks, sections of 5-7 μm were cut, stained with hematoxylin and eosin. Semi-thin 1 mm sections were obtained from Epon bricks on a Leyka ultramicrotomy. Histological preparations were examined under 10, 20, 40 lenses of a light microscope and the necessary areas were photographed. In a rat under ether anesthesia, the abdominal cavity was decapitated, and morphological changes in the stomach were studied. After macro anatomy, the stomach was isolated for further study. The experiments on laboratory animals were carried out following the Declaration of the International Medical Association, adopted in Helsinki in 1964 and completed in 2013.

The isolated stomach was fixed in solution and poured into paraffin. Then, incisions with a 6–7 mm were prepared and stained using the hematoxylin-eosin and Van Gieson methods. Histological preparations were examined under 10, 20, 40 lenses of a light microscope, and the necessary areas were photographed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Our investigation was about the morphological and morphometric changes in rats' stomach, characterize its various departments, and determine the changes in cutting fluids. We studied a gradual change in the structure of morphometric parameters of parts and layers of the stomach wall of white rats from 3 months to 6 months of age with the simultaneous use of up to 5 different types of anti-inflammatory drugs. Normally, a morphometric study of the wall of the gastric mucosa showed that the number of lymphoid follicles changes depending on age, which averaged $32.4 + 4.7$, in 3 months $37.4 + 5.7$, 4-6 months $76.4 + 7.6$. This increase in the number of cells of lymphoid follicles continues in the following months. With long-term use of NSAIDs in rats, the following changes were observed: lymphoid follicles of the stomach were undeformed, hyperplastic atypically and unevenly. Their boundaries are not determined; lymphocytes are located around the postcapillary venules. As a result of studies in the stomach wall of rats receiving antiinflammatory drugs, changes of a destructive nature were found, depending on the number of drugs. Their boundaries are not determined; lymphocytes are located around the postcapillary venules. As a result of studies in the stomach wall of rats receiving antiinflammatory drugs, changes of a destructive nature were found, depending on the number of drugs. Destructive changes are characterized by edema of the stroma of the villi, their desquamation into the lumen of the stomach, a decrease in the height of the villi, which were observed in the second group when using several types of anti-inflammatory drugs. At the same time, the observed increase in the number of goblet cells in the villi. Presumably, this is due to an increase in degenerative processes in epithelial cells under the influence of polyphragmasy.

Microscopic examination of the antrum of the stomach of white rats of the control group showed that the mucous, muscular, and serous membranes are well developed and have distinct boundaries. The mucous membrane contains many large diameter glands and smaller crypts. On the surface of the villi and crypts are cylindrical epithelial cells with oval nuclei. Among the epithelial cells are goblet cells, the most significant number of which is observed in crypts.

According to our results, the middle part of the stomach wall study shows a different degree of morphological changes when exposed to different amounts of drugs. It was found that after exposure to drugs, the size and ratio of structural components in the walls of the stomach noticeably

change. In the gastric mucosa of the experimental group of animals, intense desquamation of epithelial cells into the stomach lumen was observed at the tops of the villi. The stroma of the villi is edematous, it contains a large number of macrophages and lymphocytes, and necrosis of the villi is observed in some areas (Fig. 1).

Figure № 1. In the stomach mucous membrane, occurs edema, and the interstitial tissue is thickened due to the proliferation of fibrous connective tissue. Stain: Hematoxylin and eosin. 10x10.

2. Dystrophic and necrobiotic changes in epitheliocytes with polyphragmasy, lymphohistiocytic infiltration. Stain: Hematoxylin and eosin. 10x10.

Figure №

When taking NSAIDs, regeneration also developed atrophy of the mucous membrane, even more intensively, but the formation of normal glandular elements was blocked, and instead of them, various poorly differentiated glandular cells appeared.

Moreover, both atrophic and dystrophic changes in the mucosa deepened and prolonged use of NSAIDs in rats pathomorphologically, against the background of which catarrhal-desquamative, necroticulcerative gastritis developed.

CONCLUSION

The above facts insist on the need for further in-depth study of factors that adversely affect the mucous membrane of the stomach in various pathologies of the gastrointestinal tract. With the long-term application of more than 5 NPAs in rats pathomorphologically, catarrhal-desquamative, necrotic-ulcerative gastritis developed.

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9 ЖИЛД, 4 СОН

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